

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

Human Reference Atlas Working Group Communications

HRA Open Working Group

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Introduction

This SOP describes procedures for communicating with those involved in Human Reference Atlas (HRA) construction and usage through the HRA Open Working Group (WG). This working group guides the effort to develop tables that document agreed-upon naming conventions for Anatomical Structures, Cell Types, and Biomarkers (ASCT+B) tables and other Human Reference Atlas digital objects, which are authored by multiple consortia and support a common coordinate framework and the Human Reference Atlas.

This SOP documents the timing, tools, and processes used to communicate with members of this working group. The primary audience for this SOP is the Human Reference Atlas team at Indiana University who support this working group. Roles and responsibilities for those with a part in the procedures are listed in **Table 1**. Resources such as templates, spreadsheets, GitHub repositories, and other Materials that are used to implement the procedures are listed in **Table 2**.

Roles and Responsibilities

The **Administrative Assistant** is the primary person responsible for making sure these procedures are carried out each month, driving the timing and execution of agenda building, meeting reminders, and follow up pointers to slides and recordings. They keep the mailing list up to date.

The **HRA Lead** is responsible for setting meeting agendas, inviting speakers, gathering slides, and running the meeting.

The **Master of Ceremonies (MC)** keeps meetings running smoothly and serves as timekeeper to help presenters stay within their allotted time.

The **Videographer** manages the CNS YouTube channel and uploads video content for activities across CNS, including the meeting recordings referenced in this procedure.

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The **Working Group Scribe** takes notes capturing the decisions and action items made by the group, and assists with keeping the roll call document up to date, e.g., by adding participants that attended but did not get a chance to update the roll call document.

Table 1. Roles, names, and email addresses of key personnel.

Role	Name	Email
Administrative Assistant	Traci Smith	cnsctr@iu.edu
HRA Lead	Katy Börner	katy@iu.edu
Master of Ceremonies	Andreas Bueckle	abueckle@iu.edu
Videographer	Andreas Bueckle	abueckle@iu.edu
Working Group Scribe	Nancy Ruschman	infoccf@iu.edu

Relevant Resources

Table 2. Websites, tools, and files required for managing the HRA Open Working Group.

Name	Purpose	Location
Mailing list	Communication with working group members	https://groups.google.com/a/hubmapconsortium.org/g/ASCT-B
Experts survey	Qualtrics survey for joining the HRA Open Working Group	https://iu.co1.qualtrics.com/jfe/preview/SV_bpaBhIr8XfdiNRH?Q_CHL=preview&Q_SurveyVersionID=current
Meeting notes	Working group meeting notes	https://docs.google.com/document/d/1C2zS4YGDuT_fisOywYcxpczZet6sGbA7d4FnaX4UxVA/edit?tab=t.0#heading=h.ovpf06z5tz8
Role Call document	For recording attendance at working group meetings	https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/11_VeUtREoNyhaqfsSTCnJ5VS_nYcdLwVS-vcWnYRo2HA/edit?gid=205856788#gid=205856788
Folder for slides	Slides for all past WG meetings are collected here for WG members to access	https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1MLHQBFHHpXeZVm0kUGiukw1_3_EOyglz?usp=sharing

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Meeting recordings	View recordings of past working group meetings	HRA Working Group Meetings YouTube channel
Internal recordings folder	Location for raw footage from working group meetings	https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1I53SBdPfc73BGp4GY9DONaoFmA2feFQ
HRA Open Working Group folder	Contains most working group documents, including roll call and meeting notes	https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1RpEDN4SjJRpUIAqMYPCxGXA9xgxq9MI8?usp=drive_link

Procedures

Adding members to the working group mailing list

- Meeting invitations, meeting reminders, and post-meeting emails are shared with the working group via a Google Groups mailing list (<https://groups.google.com/a/hubmapconsortium.org/g/ASCT-B>), which is managed by the Administrative Assistant. The parent list (admin@hubmapconsortium.org) is managed by the HIVE IEC component of the HuBMAP team.
- Individuals who would like to join the working group complete a Qualtrics survey [found here](#). Please ask those who wish to join the working group to complete the survey so they will receive meeting invitations and gain access to slides and recordings.
- The Administrative Assistant reviews responses monthly for new additions, one week prior to the next working group meeting.
- The Administrative Assistant requests an upcoming agenda from the HRA Lead via email on the Monday 9 days prior to the Wednesday working group meeting.
- The Administrative Assistant adds all new participants to the Google Groups mailing list.

Sending calendar invitations

- Calendar invitations for working group meetings are sent to the mailing list once per year. The meetings should be extended rather than re-issued when the CNS recurring meeting calendar is reviewed and reissued (summer, fall semester, spring semester).
- The Administrative Assistant forwards calendar invitations to the mailing list via email. These invitations are typically added to subscriber Outlook calendars automatically but differences in spam programs and email configurations affect delivery of the calendar invitation.
- ICS files are attached to the meeting invitation, which allow for individuals using Google Calendar and other email clients to manually download and add the invitations to their calendars.

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- The meeting invitation for the particular meeting occurrence is forwarded by the Administrative Assistant to any invited presenters who are not already subscribed to the mailing list one week prior to the meeting.

Sending meeting reminders

- Email meeting reminders are sent to the mailing list one week prior to each meeting by the Administrative Assistant. An ICS meeting invitation for the specific meeting occurrence is attached to the reminder email.
- Email meeting reminders are sent to ASCT-B@hubmapconsortium.org from the cnsctr@iu.edu Outlook account.
- Meeting reminders follow the below format. The subject header for the email follows this pattern: HRA WG Meeting (insert Month, Day), 11:00a EST (or EDT if it's during Daylight Savings Time rather than Standard Time).

Hi everyone,

The next HRA Working Group meeting will be held on (insert Day, Month #).
Calls are held on the first Wednesday of each month at 11:00 am Eastern.

Slides from past meetings can be found in this folder (insert), and videos of past meetings can be found here (insert).

Agenda for next Wednesday's meeting:
(insert agenda)

Zoom link: <insert link>
Meeting ID: <insert meeting id>
Password: <insert password>

Please contact the HRA team via infoccf@iu.edu for questions and suggestions.

Thank you all,

Administrative Assistant's name

During the meeting

- The Working Group Scribe takes meeting notes in the Meeting Notes document during the meeting.

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- The scribe posts a link to the Roll Call document in the Zoom chat window at the beginning of the meeting, and reminds people to mark themselves present.
- This is repeated 5 minutes into the meeting so late-comers also get a reminder.
- Meeting participants are expected to complete the Roll Call document.
- During the meeting, the scribe takes a screenshot of the attendee window in Zoom and pastes it into the Meeting Notes document.
- Before the meeting ends, the scribe saves the Chat dialog and adds it to the meeting notes.

Meeting follow up

- After the meeting, the scribe compares the screenshot of attendees to the roll call sheet, and marks as 'present' any members who appear in the screenshot but are not marked present on the Roll Call document.
- Slides are finalized and placed in [this folder](#) by the Master of Ceremonies (MC).
- The Administrative Assistant sends a follow up email to the mailing list 24 hours after the meeting (or as soon thereafter as the recording is available). This email contains a link to the slides folder and to the HRA Working Group Meetings YouTube channel where meeting recordings are posted. Below is sample text for this reminder.

Dear HRA community,

Thank you all for a very productive meeting on Wednesday. The folder with slides for past HRA Working Group meetings can be found here:

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1MLHQBFHHPXeZVm0kUGiukwl_3_EOyglz?usp=sharing

The full playlist of meeting recordings can be found here:

<https://youtube.com/playlist?list=PL-CUnYVly7DNJc1FhqPsFPzDmd-bQD1jf>

Meeting recordings

- Meetings are set to record automatically. Once available from Kaltura via the cnsctr@iu.edu account, these recordings are uploaded to an [internal folder](#) used by the Videographer for raw video footage.
- The Videographer edits lightly if required, and uploads the video to the [HRA Working Group Meetings YouTube channel](#).
- The Videographer emails the HRA Lead and Administrative Assistant to notify them that the recording is available. It will be available within 24 hours of the meeting.

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Document storage

- Documents related to the HRA WG are stored in the [HRA Open Working Group folder](#). Access to this folder is restricted to certain individuals, but certain documents and the slide folder within are accessible to those with the link, so that all working group members can access materials. This folder contains slides from all previous meetings, the working group charter, the roll call document, and the meeting notes. The YouTube Channel can be found [here](#).

Glossary

ASCT+B tables: Anatomical Structures, Cell Types and Biomarkers (ASCT+B) Tables are authored by multiple experts across many consortia. Tables capture the paratomy of anatomical structures, cell types, and major biomarkers (such as gene, protein, lipid, or metabolic markers). Cellular identity is supported by scientific evidence and linked to ontologies.

common coordinate framework (CCF): As used in the Human Reference Atlas, this consists of ontologies and reference object libraries, computer software (e.g., user interfaces) and training materials that (1) enable biomedical experts to semantically annotate tissue samples and to precisely describe their locations in the human body (“registration”), (2) align multi-modal tissue data extracted from different individuals to a reference coordinate system (“mapping”), and to (3) provide tools for searching and browsing data at multiple levels from the whole body down to single cells (“exploration”). See also <https://hubmapconsortium.github.io/ccf/>.

Cyberinfrastructure for Network Science (CNS) Center is a research center in the Intelligent Systems Engineering Department of the Luddy School of Informatics, Computing, and Engineering at the University of Indiana Bloomington.

HuBMAP: The Human BioMolecular Atlas Program is a consortium composed of diverse research teams funded by the Common Fund at the National Institutes of Health. HuBMAP is developing the tooHRAs to create an open, global atlas of the human body at the cellular level. These tools and maps will be used to accelerate understanding of the relationships between cell and tissue organization and function and human health.

Human Reference Atlas (HRA): The Human Reference Atlas is a comprehensive, high-resolution, three-dimensional, multiscale atlas of all the cells in the healthy human body. The Human Reference Atlas provides standard terminologies and data structures for describing specimens, biological structures, and spatial positions linked to existing ontologies.

iCalendar (ICS) file: An ICS file is a calendar file saved in a universal calendar format used by several email and calendar programs, including Microsoft Outlook, Google Calendar, and Apple Calendar. It enables users to publish and share calendar information on the web and over email.

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working group (WG): a committee or group formed to study and report on a particular question and make recommendations based on its findings. Open Working Groups encourage participation from people working in other consortia rather than just those working on HuBMAP.

YouTube: A free online video-sharing platform.

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